

FAILED BUT SUCCEEDED: SUCCESS ACCOUNTS OF ENGLISH TEACHERS RE-TAKERS

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Failed But Succeeded: Success Accounts of English Teachers Re-Takers

Kristine Mae M. Sodoy,* Kristy Jane R. Muegna
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study was centralized on exploring the experiences, and challenges, the coping strategies, insights and recommendations of the English Teachers retakers who retook the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) multiple time but ultimately succeeded. Also, the study used a multiple-case study as qualitative study approach in conducting this study. The participants were three (3) English teachers' retakers and three (3) informants, and now currently teaching at DepEd. Results of the study found that these English teachers who retake the Licensure Examination for Teachers for a quite number of times but eventually succeeded also experienced difficulty in seeking job, they gain self-confidence, understanding that teaching in the field goes beyond acquiring a license, and being determined and courageous. They overcome these by having family as a pillar of support, imbibing faith as a source of strength, being hopeful of the right time and thinking of family's future, sacrifices, and educational goals. The informants, too, shared that even though you failed many times, it is not the reason to give up. Hence, the study recommended that everyone should keep pushing forward despite of challenges, everything will not go as planned, we have to keep our faith and trust to the Lord. Additionally, the most important is before you take an exam you really need to be prepared and equipped your mind with everything needed in order to pass.

Keywords: *english teachers retakers, licensure examination (LET), multiple-case study, qualitative inquiry, philippines*

Introduction

Becoming a professional teacher involves dedicated effort in passing the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET), mandated by the Department of Education (DepEd). Teaching eligibility requires a degree in education, specified in either secondary or elementary education, under Republic Act No. 7836, the "Philippine Teachers Professionalization Act of 1994." This pivotal board examination, integral to the Act, seeks to enhance supervision and regulation within the teaching profession. Recognizing the crucial role of teachers in nation-building, the State underscores quality education through effective oversight of the licensure examination for the professionalization of teaching (PRC), emphasizing its role as gateway to a teaching career (Yauney, 2022).

In Europe, where licenses take precedence as the primary and essential requirement for obtaining teaching positions, mandating a minimum of 2 years of licensed experience. Particularly concerning English teachers in Europe, some face the challenge of re-taking the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET). Despite initial obstacles, their eventual success highlights the resilience and determination of English educators to fulfill demanding licensure criteria. This emphasizes their dedication to professional development and ongoing learning within the challenging framework of teaching qualifications in European nations (Algate, 2022).

In Cavite State University in the Philippines, a scrutiny of candidates' performance ratings reveals a worrisome pattern of low scores in licensure exams, particularly among non-passers. According to the study of Antiojo (2017), the pressing need for intervention to address this concerning trend, anticipating a further decline in the coming years. Nationally, Teacher Education Institutions witness a significant downturn, with graduates from these courses achieving a mere 31% average passing rate, notably lower than success rates in other board exams. The decline is further highlighted by disheartening passing rates of 11% for elementary education and 26% for secondary education. These unsettling statistics mirror the experiences of English teachers, who, as re-takers, grapple with improving their licensure exam scores. The broader context of diminishing performance in Teacher Education Institutions underscores the struggles and determination of individual educators to overcome obstacles in attaining licensure success. The urgent call for intervention in academic institutions aligns with the efforts of these English teachers who, despite initial setbacks, persist in seeking professional recognition (Mateo, 2017).

Examining the experiences of English teachers who undergo the process of retaking Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) is crucial for gaining a comprehensive understanding of both their successes and the challenges they encounter. This research carries a sense of urgency to reveal critical factors that influence success, aiming to enhance teacher preparation, support systems, and educational policies promptly. The societal importance of this study is evident in its ability to inspire resilience within the teaching community, showcasing how perseverance transforms setbacks into opportunities for professional development. The exploration of these English teachers' journeys is indispensable for fostering a culture of continuous improvement in education, providing compelling examples that motivate both current and aspiring teachers to persist amid challenges.

In connection with this, recent related studies have been conducted related to this study such as the study conducted by Amanonce (2020) entitled, "Licensure Examination Performance and Academic Achievement of Teacher Education Graduates" which focuses on correlating academic achievement with licensure exam performance among teacher education graduates. However, this study is different as it delves into specific experiences and challenges of those who initially failed but later succeeded in licensure exams. On

the other hand, Binayao & Dales (2020) conducted a study entitled, “A Phenomenological Study of the Passers and Non-Passers in the Licensure Examination for Teachers” which explores the lived experiences of passers and non-passers in the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) at Bukidnon State University. However, this study is different as it provides a distinct narrative and this study is different from the study of Sanchez et. al. (2023) entitled, “Performance of Beginning Teachers in the Licensure Examination for Teachers: A National Study” which aims to explore the overall performance of beginning teachers in the licensure examination for teachers. However, these studies did not delve into the challenges, strategies, and personal stories of individuals who successfully navigated initial obstacles in English teaching licensure exams.

The comprehensive findings of this mixed-methods study will be widely disseminated to various stakeholders, ensuring that the insights gleaned from this research reach a diverse audience. The study’s outcomes will be shared with education students, their parents and educators, allowing them to benefit from the knowledge generated by this investigation. Furthermore, academic institutions and their faculty research committees will receive the research findings, providing valuable input for enhancing teacher training programs and language education practices. The technical panel members and research ethics committee will also have access to the results, ensuring the ethical conduct of research and adherence to quality standards.

Research Questions

The main goal of this study explored the experiences and coping mechanism of English teachers’ re-takers. For these reasons, there were important questions tackled and these were as follows:

1. What are the experiences of English Teachers retaking the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET)?
2. How did the English teachers’ re-takers cope with the challenges that they have experienced?
3. What are the insights that can be drawn from the experiences of English Teachers in retaking the Licensure examination that can be shared with their peer and with others in general?

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative research methodology based on various case studies, to more fully comprehend the in-depth analysis of the informants' experiences. Qualitative researchers should adopt this approach. To direct and support the development of hypotheses, it uses in-depth and focus investigations of small groups of people. According to Neubauer et. al. (2019), the findings of qualitative research are regarded as descriptive rather than predictive. The technique also aids in the researcher's ability to connect with the participants. Therefore, the researcher might report to the participants for further clarification and verification in order to make the data more reliable and authentic.

In this study, in order to obtain a deeper understanding of the experiences of the participants, qualitative research design emphasizes exploring the experiences and perceptions of individuals in their natural setting. This study aims to provide rich and nuanced descriptions of participant experiences, which is an important aspect of qualitative research. Furthermore, the study did not explore different therapies or use correlational or experimental methods to measure variables. This approach is appropriate for the research question and ensures that the study is focused on understanding the experiences and perceptions of the participants, instead of reducing them to variables and numbers.

The design of this research was considered qualitative. One form of qualitative research method is a multiple-case study. According to Cresswell (2013), the use of a multiple-case study design in qualitative research is a powerful tool for exploring complex systems with in-depth data collection. By examining multiple cases, researchers can gain a wider understanding of their research question and theoretical evolution. This design is particularly useful for exploring real-life multiple-bounded systems with many sources of information, such as information management in the WIL process. Multiple-case designs allow researchers to address behavioral conditions and understand complex issues by exploring differences and similarities between cases. Using a multiple-case design enables researchers to obtain interpretative perspectives from participants, providing a holistic and in-depth explanation beyond quantitative statistical results (Zainal, 2007).

This study entailed a thorough investigation of real-life, intricate systems by collecting extensive data from various sources. Through the application of a multiple- case design, the researcher aims to achieve a more comprehensive grasp of the research question and theoretical development. The primary focus is on comprehending how information is handled in the context of Work-Integrated Learning (WIL) across the three distinct cases under examination, which provides a deeper insight into complex issues and the dynamics of behavior within this system. This approach draws on the perspectives and experiences of participants involved in managing information during the WIL process, enabling a profound and well-rounded understanding. Ultimately, the multiple-case design offers a comprehensive and insightful explanation of information management in WIL, going beyond mere quantitative data to explore the subtleties of participant experiences and practices.

Participants

In this study, there were three (3) participants and three (3) informants selected for their characteristics and willingness to participate.

All participants were English teacher re-takers. The study aimed to investigate the factors influencing the success of English teacher re-takers, particularly those who have encountered setbacks in their licensure exams but ultimately prevailed. By studying the experiences of English teacher re-takers, the research seeks to uncover the challenges they face and provide valuable insights to develop supportive strategies and interventions for educators facing similar hurdles in their professional careers.

The participants for this study were chosen based on specific criteria: In Case 1 there was one (1) participant and one (1) informant, both English teachers who have re-taken the licensure exam three (3) times; Case 2 featured one (1) participant and one (1) informant, both English teachers who have re-taken the licensure exam four (4) times; and Case 3 comprises one (1) participant and one (1) informant, both English teachers who have re-taken the licensure exam five (5) times. Each distinct case showcased the unique journey and triumph of English teachers who, despite facing various challenges, have succeeded in their profession after multiple times of retaking the license exam. This demographic data illuminated the diverse aspects of their lives, aiding in the development of impactful interventions to assist them on their path to achievement.

Procedure

Qualitative research offered an extensive array of data collection techniques. Focus group discussions (FGDs) and in-depth interviews (IDIs) were the most popular research procedures. Qualitative research involved having conversations or talks with individuals to gain a deeper understanding of their opinions on the study issue and the reasons behind them (Manu, 2018).

To involve participants in the online search, explain the study to them, and obtain their permission, a researcher needed a thorough understanding of the nature and goal of the research. The procedures utilized to collect the data required for the study began with the application of the purposive sampling technique to identify the informants.

Initially, individuals were required to carefully read and comprehend the consent and agreement forms before signing them. These forms included the necessary condition that informants be willing to share their expertise and that their involvement be voluntary, both of which were critical to the success of the study. Additionally, a research orientation was provided to the informants. The orientation covered the goal of the interview, its duration, and its level of confidentiality. The researcher also considered the informants' claims that participation in the study would benefit them. Both focus group discussions and in-depth interviews required that each participant be treated separately. Similarly, an essential component of comprehending particular theories was qualitative research. While quantitative data aided in explaining prevailing attitudes and actions, qualitative data aimed to elucidate and depict the factors that shaped behavioral viewpoints (Lauri, 2019).

Data Analysis

In this research study, the data gathered were presented and analyzed based on the needs and objectives of the research endeavor. In order to generate the findings of the study, sufficient analysis of the content of the participants' responses were done.

Thus, the goal of data analysis is to find for common patterns that will disclose ideas, which may answer the research questions being established in this study.

Performing a systematic search and organization of interview transcripts, observation notes, or other non-textual materials were referred to as qualitative data analysis, according to Lune and Beng (2017). This procedure was carried out to give the researcher the opportunity to gather information and to improve public comprehension of the phenomenon or research issue.

The replies from the participants in this study will be collected, transcribed, and then were translated from their original languages into Standard English. The primary source of data for this study's data analysis were the transcripts. To extract the study's conclusions, the data undergo a number of treatments and processing steps.

The next step for the researcher were a qualitative topic analysis. One of the most popular types of analysis which is reading over a data set, such as the transcripts from in-depth interviews or focus groups, and looking for patterns in meaning to extract themes. Thematic analysis involves an active reflexive process in which the researcher's personal experience is crucial to extracting meaning from the data. When seeing trends in data, learning about qualitative analysis, and incorporating research subjects in the analysis process, thematic analysis should be taken into consideration (Delve, 2020).

In this multiple case study, the researcher organized and analyzed various themes identified through a detailed coding process. By examining the similarities among the ideas and codes, she identified key themes that capture the essence of the phenomenon under investigation. Emerging themes were used to construct a comprehensive description of the studied subject. The researcher thoroughly explored and elaborated on these themes to offer a clear and detailed depiction, which facilitates drawing well-founded conclusions and validating the findings. Finally, data reduction was used in analyzing the data. This means that this employed of deleting unnecessary data and modifying them into a useful material for the sake of the study. This is for the purpose of making the data comprehensible to the readers. The researcher purified the data and removed the information or samples which do not carry much information essential on the inquiry at hand (Sutton & Austin, 2015).

Ethical Considerations

When it comes to research, ethics refer to the norms and values that guide decisions regarding the collection of data and analysis of said data, as well as the dissemination of findings. As 'ethical knowledge is of a tacit character more often than not' (Gedutis et al., 2022), an increasing number of studies are investigating the ethical challenges posed by research evaluation. This paper aims to increase the awareness of novice researchers regarding the most common ethical issues that they need to give their utmost attention to while conducting research which involves living participants. Specifically, this paper focus on the following:

Respect all participants must be treated equally and must receive close consideration for every point they make during the investigation. BERA (2018) for instance note that researchers should operate within an ethic of respect for any persons – including themselves – involved in or touched by the research they are undertaking. Individuals should be treated fairly, sensitively, and with dignity and freedom from prejudice, in recognition of both their rights and of differences arising from age, gender, sexuality, ethnicity class, nationality, cultural identity, partnership status, faith, disability, political belief or any other significant characteristic.

In this study, the researcher developed informed consent documents for the study's participants. These documents were distributed to the chosen participants as the study progressed. Prior to conducting interviews, the researcher requested permission from the participants to record the interview sessions. Additionally, the researcher prioritized establishing a positive rapport, fostering a sense of friendship, trust, and confidence with the participants.

Benevolence the user's data must not be 'triangulated' in such a way that the researcher reveals potentially damaging information that the user did not originally intend to share. However, when researchers collect data on internet-based platforms, it may not be possible to notify all participants when there is a privacy breach (Viljoen & Cilliers 2018).

In this study, the researcher implemented rigorous measures to safeguard the data collected, including voice recordings, transcripts, notes, and related materials, to prevent unauthorized access and data leaks. To ensure the utmost security and privacy of the participants, all acquired data including any personal information, was encrypted and kept in a secure manner. Furthermore, pseudonyms were used to anonymize and protect the identity of the study participants.

Justice necessitates a fair distribution of the risks and rewards based on the findings of the investigation. Therefore, it is important to recognize the contributions of each participant because they are crucial to the success of this study. In all of their endeavors, they must receive the proper credit (Bloom & Crabtree, 2006).

In this study, the researcher was committed to the principle of fair treatment for all research participants. The anonymity and confidentiality of the participants were rigorously protected. The researcher refrained from revealing any personal biases and avoided presenting any interpretations that were influenced by their own perspective when discussing the potential findings of the study.

Confidentiality in research ethics, the crucial principle of confidentiality entails an obligation on the part of the researcher to ensure that any use of information obtained from or shared by human subjects respects the dignity and autonomy of the participant, and does not violate the interests of individuals or communities (see Box 7.2 for clarification of concepts). The right to confidentiality in research is recognized in international bio-ethical guidelines, such as the 'Helsinki Declaration' (last updated in 2013), and the European General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, effective 2018).

In this study, the researcher implemented stringent measures to ensure the confidentiality and security of the data collected, encompassing voice recordings, encrypted transcripts, notes, and related materials. To safeguard the participants, all acquired data including personal details, were subjected to encryption and robust security protocols. Furthermore, pseudonyms were utilized to preserve and shield the anonymity of the study participants.

Consent, the only agreement seems to be, is that while there are numerous methods available for obtaining consent, there is no clear best practice for researchers to follow when seeking consent from virtual subjects. This situation creates a challenge for researchers, as they must navigate through various approaches without a definitive standard to guide them. The diversity in methods and the absence of a universally accepted practice means that researchers may adopt different strategies based on their specific contexts and the nature of their research (Hibbin et al., 2018).

In this study, participants were actively encouraged to make well-informed and voluntary decisions regarding their involvement. The researcher ensured that all individuals taking part in the study are enthusiastic and willing participants. Obtaining consent from the study participants to record their responses and share their experiences for data collection is a fundamental step. Participants were also fully informed about their rights, including the right to pose questions during the interview, the option to discontinue the interview without providing a rationale, and the right to decline answering sensitive questions. The researcher fully respected the participants' choice to exit the interview if they decide to do so.

Results and Discussion

This section was divided into the following sections. Part one (1) dealt with the data provided by the participants, which was used to generate the qualitative data. Part two (2) delved into the data analysis processes as well as the steps involved in categorizing emergent themes based on the results of in-depth interviews (IDI) each case. Part three (3) outlined the replies gathered during the data gathering procedure.

Participants

The participants of the study were three (3) English teachers who retook the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) multiple times. All participants were female. By that, the researcher put her trust on them that they could supply what this study sought to find out.

The interviews took place inside the campus, and the researcher spoke with them about where they preferred to be interviewed. The researcher got where they wanted to go, both the interviewer and interviewee were pleased with the end result, resulting in a seamless flow and open communication whenever extra or probing questions were required. Participants had the option of refusing to answer any question that they deemed unprofitable or against their choice. The data collected during the interviews was kept in strict discretion to guarantee confidentiality, and only the researcher and participants had access to any information that was expressed but not included due to the study's nature.

To adhere to the data collecting method, the researcher used her cellphone in place of the required tape recorder to record replies of the participants, as well as notepad to write down notes on the session's events. All of them complied all the request, with the exception of one that their identities be kept anonymous in the research (Boyce & Neala, 2006).

Categorization of Data

The voice recorded discussions were transcribed, translated and analyzed once the in-depth interviews were completed. The researcher initiated the analysis with the process of coding.

Coding is a technique of organizing the assets into pieces of content fragments some time recently giving meaning to information. The coding strategy was utilized to supply a depiction of the setting of individuals as well as the categories of topics to be analyzed. These subjects were utilized to assist frame a wide depiction of the marvels Beneath examination.

Table 1. Participants of the Study

<i>Pseudonym</i>	<i>Age</i>	<i>Gender</i>	<i>School</i>	<i>Code</i>
Light	31	Female	San Miguel Elem. School	Idi - 01
Smart	46	Female	Sawata Ernandcor Central Elementary School	Idi - 02
Grace	38	Female	Sagayen National High School	Idi - 03

For the information to the categorized, the topics were displayed by inquire about address and alluded to as manor themes. The subjects that had developed from the think about were talked about and explain altogether to supply a striking depiction. At that point came the drawing of the conclusion and confirmation, that point within the ponder in which the preparatory thoughts and designs approximately the discoveries and created (Miles & Huberman, 1994).

The researcher took notice of the constructs of credibility, dependability, transferability, and conformity in order to add trustworthiness to our study. In addition to the triangulation approach, member verification was done to address credibility. This was achieved by giving participants a copy of the interview transcript so they could provide comments and attest to its accuracy. So far, none of the informants have raised any objection to the transcript or provided any input to the contrary. They all signed that participant's verification form to confirm their affirmative response. The study's triangulation was made possible by the fact that it included more than two sources specifically, readings from related literature and participants (Guba et al., 2003).

The researcher applied an audit trail that was referred to ensure dependability and confirm ability. It was created to allow the research review panel to confirm our results, assumptions, and conjectures (Carcary, 2009).

In terms of transferability, the researcher stated from the beginning that the results could not be generalized because these views were based only on the participants own experiences in the indicated localities. Nonetheless, researcher agreed that when the credibility, confirm ability, and dependability of a qualitative case study are assured, then transferability is addressed as well (Gempes et al., 2009).

Case 1 – Light

Light is a 31 years old English teacher who retook the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) for three (3) times and who is currently teaching at San Miguel Elementary School. She is been teaching for about three (3) years in Department of Education (DepEd). I asked her what name she wants to hide her identity and she said, Light.

She admitted that it is a big challenge for her to be a retaker, repeatedly retaking the LET exam is tough due to the stress, time, and financial burden it brought, along with the emotional strain of constant failure.

However, perseverance and keep trying eventually succeeded because of their determination, hard work, having faith in God, and willingness to learn from past mistakes. Despite the hurdles, success brings a sense of accomplishment and opens doors to fulfilling career opportunities, making the journey worthwhile in the end.

Research Question No. 1: What are the experiences of English Teachers in retaking the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET)?

Based on the first research question, there were many themes that have found and these were the themes that had emerged. These were as followed below.

Strengthening one's Self-Esteem

In the first question, the researcher asked her about her experiences as an English Teacher Retaker who successfully passed the LET exam after retaking it three (3) times. She said that she really gained confidence after she passed.

"...Passing the LET has made a big impact on me as a teacher and especially I gain more self- confidence, to be Strong-willed, courageous, not to give up easily on life's challenges." (IDI-R1)

In line with this, Shimmer supported that passing the Licensure Examination for Teacher (LET) after retaking it how many times, it really uplifted her confidence, be more courageous, and optimistic as it means that she's getting closer to achieve her dreams.

"Passing the LET make me more courageous and optimistic in everything, feels like getting closer towards our dreams..." (Inf-C1)

Persevering in the Midst of Adversity

Knowing that there are steps to follow before getting a job in a department shows that she understood what is needed. Light also told the researcher that, even if it's hard and there are problems along the way, you keep going. Light also show that she is strong, would not give up easily, and ready to face any difficulties and keep moving forward until she reach her goal.

"...there are processes to go through before I can work in the department, but its okay, I did not complain because I believe that there is right timing as long as you do all the efforts to achieve what you want." (IDI-R1)

This was supported by Shimmer. She said that, even though they already have the license it means you can easily get job. Applying a job requires patience since there are process and requirements that they need to comply and wait patiently.

"Yes, after passing the LET we have to go through with the processes in applying a job in the DepEd. Where it really requires patience since teaching is our dream then we have to wait patiently." (Inf-C1)

Difficulty in Seeking Job

Light came across different experiences that finding a job can be really tough, even when she already qualified like having a license for teaching. Even though she faced a lot of rejections along the way, she did not let it stop her. She kept trying until she finally landed a job, despite the challenges, she was determined to keep going until she achieved her goal of securing employment as a teacher.

"...seeking job is not easy, I still went through many rejections even though I have a license but I just kept going until I got a job." (IDI-R1)

Shimmer supported that it is true, that applying a job or a position of Teacher I in DepEd is not easy, because there are still many processes to go through just like to rank up in order for to apply and have a permanent item.

"Applying for Teacher-I position is not easy. You have to with the processes and wait for the permanent item in the DepEd." (Inf-C1)

Persevering in the Midst of Adversity

Despite passing the exam and obtaining the necessary license, there are additional processes required before being able to work in the department. Rather than becoming discouraged or complaining about the situation, Light maintained a positive outlook and believes in the concept of timing. Light shares her resilience and determination, as she continued to make efforts towards her goal despite the delays or obstacles encountered. By remaining patient and focused on her efforts, she demonstrated a willingness to overcome challenges and trust that her hard work will eventually lead her to achieving her desired outcome.

"...Even though I passed the exam and have the license already, there are processes to go through before I can work in the department, but it is okay, I did not complain because I believe that there is right timing as long as you do all the efforts to achieve what you want." (IDI-R1)

Research Question No. 2: How did the English Teachers re-takers cope with the challenges that they have experienced?

In the second question, Light was asked about how she cope with the challenges that she experienced after successfully passed the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET). The following themes stated below were thoroughly and were carefully reflected.

Having Family as a Pillar of Support

The researcher asked Light about how she overcome the challenges that she experienced after successfully passing the LET. She told the researcher that she has her family in overcoming challenges, her family supports her and give her motivation and encouragement to keep pushing forward. Furthermore, she told the researcher that her family is her very first inspiration to pursue despite of challenges, that sometimes she doubted herself.

"...My family, they never stopped giving me love, encouragement and support to keep going until I passed, that even sometimes I doubt about myself but because of them they always ignite the fire within me to keep pushing forward. That's why I did everything for them. They are my inspiration along with the help of grace of our Lord." (IDI-R1)

Shimmer confirmed that, having the support of family enable her to keep going. Knowing that loved ones are consistently present through life's highs and lows cultivates a sense of security and resilience.

"Family and God served as a support system in facing different challenges they are always there through ups and downs." (Inf-C1)

Imbibing Faith as a Source of Strength

The researcher inquired about how Light managed the pressure of meeting the expectations and standards of being an English teacher after passing the LET. She said when she felt stressed and nervous, she prayed to God and ask for help and guidance, because nothing is impossible in the will of the Lord. She said:

"..Honestly, I feel pressure and nervous but I'm always praying to God to help me, guide me, and give me knowledge and wisdom to become an effective teacher to my students" (IDI-R1)

Shimmer confirmed that having strong faith in God makes a person strong, that enable an individual to face challenges as well as able to manage pressures in the field of teaching.

"Having strong faith in God and positivity. These are the things we have to be able to manage the pressures and standards of being an English teacher." (Inf-C1)

Being Hopeful of the Right Time

The researcher asked Light about how she maintained a positive mindset as she faced challenges and pressure associated with passing the LET. Light expressed that faith in the Lord helped her to maintain a positive perspective, confident that the right opportunity to work in DEPED will come at the right time. She also shared to the researcher that waiting for something patiently coupled with trust in God is worth it. She said:

"...will just think about my family and the Lord's will, I know for myself that when the right time comes, I will be given an item and I can work in DEPED." (IDI-R1)

Shimmer supported that having a positive outlook and believing in God's perfect timing will have a positive return. Everything has its perfect timing and should not rush everything. She also stated that before getting the stage of waiting to be employed, she spent how many years studying and get her degree to be a teacher, therefore, she should not surrender and wait patiently.

"Having a positive outlook that God will always provide and believing to herself that there's a perfect time to everything, always put in mind that before we get this point in life, that we studied for how many years so this is not the time to surrender." (Inf-C1)

Thinking of Family's Future, Sacrifices, and Educational Goals

Light highlighted that her desire to secure her family's future, coupled with the personal dream of becoming a teacher, served as her driving force amidst challenges. This steadfast commitment reflects her unwavering determination to overcome obstacles and achieve both personal and familial goals, embodying resilience and dedication in the face of adversity.

Shimmer supported Light's statement that family's future is one of the reasons why she kept on trying and retake multiple times, even until now that she is already teaching. She added that, thinking about family's sacrifices for her makes her stronger to face any adversities and do her best.

"Thinking about family's future gives me motivation to keep going in pursuing teaching despite everything or challenges being experienced." (Inf- C1)

Research Question No. 3: What are the insights that can be drawn from the experiences of English Teachers in retaking the Licensure examination that can be shared with their peer and with others in general?

In the third question, it was highlighted the lessons gleaned from the journey of English teacher who undergo the process of retaking the licensure examination can offer valuable wisdom to their colleagues and the wider community. Below were the following themes that emerged during the study.

Pushing Forward Despite Failures

The researcher inquired Light about her retake journey play a role in shaping her resilience and perseverance as a teacher. Light shared that she learned to stay strong, keep her determination high, and never give up on her dreams, even when faced with many setbacks. She also accounted that not to lose hope, failures are part of success and it is not a reason to stop achieving her dreams.

"Being a retaker has given me a big role to be strong, full of will not to lose hope, and still achieving dreams even though there are

many failures.” (IDI-R1)

Shimmer supported that failing means you are weak however; it makes a person to keep doing their best and determined. Being a retaker is not easy, wherein they receive a lot of criticism but despite of that it makes her braver and stronger and make failures as motivation to move forward.

“LET retake make you stronger and braver. It also encouraged us to be more determined and patient to not lose hope” (Inf-C1)

Being Prepared for Any Teaching Tasks

Light shared that before taking an exam or teaching a lesson, preparation is the key. Just as to studying well before an exam, it is important to thoroughly understand the material before teaching it to students. Being well-prepared ensures that you can effectively explain concepts and answer questions, just like a soldier prepares for battle before entering the war.

“Before you enter a big war, you must be prepared. Before you take the exam, make sure that you studied well. Just like teaching students before you discuss your lesson, make sure you are well prepared, and know the lesson very well so that if the student has a question, you can explain it to them well.” (IDI-R1)

This was supported by Shimmer as the informant stating that being well prepared is imperative to get the success we want to achieve. Being prepared will greatly helped a teacher to teach effectively and students to learn effectively.

“It really requires you to be prepared at all times and have a positive mindset and faith in God.” (Inf- C1)

Cultivating Inspiration

The researcher asked Light about the goals she set for herself as a licensed teacher who experienced to take the LET exam for a quite number of times. Light shared that she will not take for granted the Lord has given to her. She will be passionate to her job as a teacher, impart learning to the students and inspiring everyone using her journey as a retaker to not give up to any challenges to achieve goals.

“The goal I have set for myself is that I will not waste the favor given by the Lord. I will use it for the goodness that can give a great help to the children and be an inspiration to others.” (IDI-R1)

Having Positive Outlook

The researcher inquired Light’s valuable insights she gained as someone who retook the LET and is now a licensed teacher that could probably help other English teachers facing similar challenges. Light shared that maintaining determination and seeking guidance and assistance from a higher power, trusting that He will give it at the right time.

“Just keep going, do not give up, make an effort and ask the Lord for help because He will always give it in His right timing.” (IDI-R1)

Shimmer supported Light’s claim that whatever may happen, never lose hope. If you have dream you have to exert effort to achieve it. Always be positive to the outcomes. Everyone experienced failures before succeeded.

“Never lose hope, just keep going and wait for Gods will. Always think positive and be strong. Failures is just a test.” (Inf-C1)

Case 2 – Smart

Smart is a 46 years old English teacher who retook the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) for three (4) times and who is currently teaching at Sawata Ernandcor Central Elementary School. She is been teaching for about nine (9) years in Department of Education (DepEd). I asked her what name she wants to hide her identity and she said, Smart.

She admitted that being a retaker is not easy because based on her experiences, she received many judgments from other people that she is not smart enough to be a teacher, but she just keeps going, have self-review and equipped herself with learnings, and do her best in taking the exam.

Even though sometimes she may feel down and unmotivated because of failures she experienced, her family elevate her to keep pushing forward until she passed the Licensure exam. Despite the hurdles, success brings a sense of accomplishment and opens doors to fulfilling career opportunities, making the journey worthwhile in the end.

Research Question No. 1: What are the experiences of English Teachers in retaking the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET)?

Based on the first research question, there were many themes that have found and these were the themes that had emerged. These were as follows:

Experiencing Difficulty in Seeking Job

Smart encountered rejections while applying for jobs. She mentioned that job applications were among the most challenging

experiences she faced. However, despite the obstacles, she persevered with determination, holding onto a positive attitude and unwavering dedication to her objective. This mindset aided her in overcoming any feelings of discouragement or self-doubt that surfaced due to repeated failures.

“Seeking a job after passing the examination is one of the toughest stages I have experienced, wherein I experienced a lot of rejections.” (IDI-R2)

This was supported by Witty, hiring process often involves stringent requirements, including specific qualifications, certifications, and experience, which can make it difficult for aspiring teachers to secure employment wherein if these are not met, they are rejected.

“It also takes time to find job wherein you may experience rejections in applying if you did not meet the qualifications.” Inf-C2

Building Self-Confidence

Passing an examination opens doors to new opportunities, such as teaching positions in classrooms or institutions, it also opens avenues for personal and professional growth. Smart shared that when she finally passed the LET it really boost her confidence as she is one step closer to her dream to teach students in an institution. She accounted that:

“Personally, passing the examination uplift my confidence as it is a passport in being able to teach in the classroom or in institution.” (IDI-R2)

Witty, the informant affirmed that passing the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET), can significantly boost self-confidence. Successfully overcoming the challenges and sacrifices required to pass the LET reinforces a sense of accomplishment and validates one's efforts. She stated that:

“It is true that we gain more self-confidence, because it means that our sacrifices and hurdles paid off and being positive in life, and full of will to share learnings to learners.” (Inf-C2)

Being Determined and Courageous

Being determined and courageous fuels the individual's commitment to their goal, motivating them to continue striving for success despite past disappointments. Smart shared that having determination and courage helped her a lot to pass the LET. This perseverance in the face of challenges not only demonstrates resilience but also reinforces self-belief and resilience.

“Having a strong determination contributed a lot to me. Failing an examination once is not a hindrance in achieving one's goal. Being determined and having enough courage to take again the examination, be able to give my best, and be able to pass the examination.” (IDI-R2)

Witty supported the claim of Smart that pivotal role of determination and courage in overcoming challenges and pursuing goals. Facing such challenges becomes a test of one's resilience and determination, representing a commitment to achieving success, demonstrating an unwavering belief in one's abilities and aspirations. Witty stipulated that:

“Having determination and courage play a big role in order to surpass challenges and to pursue because even though retaking multiple times Facing these challenges will really measure your determination, passing the LET is our great achievement.” (Inf-C2)

Understanding that Teaching in the Field Goes Beyond Acquiring a License

Licensure serves as a crucial gateway into a profession, marking the initial step on a path of continuous learning and development. It symbolizes the culmination of years of education and preparation, Smart shared that it signifies not the endpoint but rather the beginning of a lifelong journey of growth and refinement. Obtaining the license represents a significant milestone, affirming one's competence and readiness to practice in their chosen field. However, it also signifies the start of new opportunities for professional advancement, specialization, and contribution to the field.

“Passing the Licensure examination does not mean you have reached your goal, because I personally, waited for my chance to finally teach in the classroom and it is another stage in my life which I find difficult.” (IDI-R2)

As Witty supported that securing a teaching position can be challenging due to specific requirements set by schools or educational institutions. Therefore, despite passing the LET, individuals may face further hurdles in their journey to become educators. Passing the LET is a crucial milestone, it marks just the beginning of the process toward becoming a fully-fledged teacher.

“It does not mean that you passed the LET you can teach already, because you have to wait or apply job which is not easy.” (Inf-C2)

Research Question No. 2: How did the English Teachers re-takers cope with the challenges that they have experienced?

In the second question, Smart was asked about how she cope with the challenges that she experienced after successfully passed the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET). The following themes stated below were thoroughly and were carefully reflected.

Considering Family as a Pillar of Support

Smart shared that her family plays as a source of inspiration and motivation in her journey to become a teacher. Their unwavering support and encouragement provide her with the strength and determination to persevere through challenges, even after facing setbacks. The love and belief her family has in her abilities instill a sense of responsibility and commitment to achieving her goals, driving her to continue striving until she succeeds, their support serves as a constant reminder of the importance of her aspirations, reinforcing her resolve to overcome obstacles and fulfill her dreams.

“My family is one of my inspirations and source of motivation to try again until I passed and became a teacher.” (IDI-R2)

Witty confirmed Smart's assertion the pivotal role of family as an unwavering source of motivation and support. Their constant presence and encouragement serve as a driving force, fueling her to persist in her endeavors despite obstacles. Additionally, her prayers and belief in the individual's potential provide a sense of reassurance and strength, reinforcing their determination to achieve success.

“Family is one of motivation to never stop trying, who always by our side supporting us and praying to God until we passed.” (Inf-C2)

Practicing Gratitude in Any Circumstances

Practicing gratitude, she cultivated a positive mindset, recognizing the value in every experience and setback along the way. Smart shared the importance of gratitude, self-belief, and patience in her journey to pass the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET). Believing in herself and maintaining faith in the process enables her to persevere through challenges, trusting that her efforts will yield results in due time., Smart highlights the significance of resilience, self-assurance, and trust in the journey toward achieving her goal of passing the LET.

“Practicing gratitude, being thankful to everything, believe in myself because every prayer comes with an answer and everything has its perfect timing.” (IDI-R2)

This was supported by Witty that maintaining faith in God's plan and expressing gratitude for each step of the journey, she finds solace and guidance in the process. She enabled to life's uncertainties with resilience and optimism, knowing that every experience contributes to her growth and eventual success.

“Always believing that there is a perfect timing for everything. Waiting for the right time for her, praying to God and thanking God for everything.” (Inf-C2)

Smart shared the effectiveness of focusing on specific goals and adjusting expectations to alleviate pressure. By directing her attention towards achievable objectives, she maintains clarity and purpose in navigating her professional journey. Lowering expectations allows her to alleviate the burden of meeting standards, enabling her to approach challenges with a balanced perspective. This strategy empowered Smart to effectively manage stress and maintain momentum in her endeavors.

“Focusing on goals and lowering expectations helped me manage the pressure of the environment after passing the examination.” (IDI- R2)

Witty supported Smart's assertion that pressure is always there, particularly for newly licensed teachers, buy prioritizing objectives and putting forth their best effort, individuals can effectively navigate the expectations surrounding their new role. This approach empowers her as a newly licensed teacher to manage pressure while pursuing professional growth and success.

“Pressure is always there but, focusing on goal and doing your best makes you manage the expectations around as newly licensed teacher.” (Inf-C2)

Reclaiming Focus and Faith

Regaining control over one's attention and trust in a higher power after experiencing distractions or doubts. Smart shared the importance of self-acceptance and resilience in the face of external expectations. By recognizing that it's acceptable not to meet others' standards, she relieves herself of unnecessary pressure and fosters a sense of self-compassion. Remaining focused on giving her best effort enables her to maintain clarity and purpose in her endeavors. Additionally, seeking guidance through prayer demonstrates her reliance on faith as a source of strength and guidance in navigating challenges.

“Reminding myself that it is okay if I did not do or meet their expectations and standards, as long as I did my best, remain focus and always praying to God and ask for guidance.” (IDI-R2)

Research Question No. 3: What are the insights that can be drawn from the experiences of English Teachers in retaking the Licensure examination that can be shared with their peer and with others in general?

In the third question, it was highlighted the lessons gleaned from the journey of English teacher who undergo the process of retaking the licensure examination can offer valuable wisdom to their colleagues and the wider community. Below were the following themes that emerged during the study.

Commitment to One's Chosen Profession

A profound commitment to the profession, indicating a strong sense of responsibility and appreciation for the opportunity. Smart shared after she passed the LET, she will never waste nor take for granted the chance has given to her, and be more passionate and dedicated as a teacher.

“It makes me more dedicated to my profession. I will never waste or take for granted this opportunity or chance given to me. I will forever be passionate to this.” (IDI-R2)

Overcoming the challenges of being a retaker and successfully passing the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) can significantly bolster one's confidence and dedication to the teaching profession. Witty supported the assertion of Smart that achieving licensure validates their perseverance and competence, instilling a sense of pride and belief in their abilities. This newfound confidence and dedication serve as driving forces, inspiring them to contribute meaningfully to their profession and continue striving for excellence.

“Being a retaker, passing the LET and be a licensed teacher would greatly impact to our confidence and be dedicated to profession” (Inf- C2)

Preparation Leads to Success

Preparing well for the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) helped the individual to understand what to expect and how to answer questions effectively, increasing the chances of passing. Smart asserted that failure as a stepping stone to success and advocates for continuous effort and improvement.

“It is better to fail than not trying at all, it is okay to fail but it is not okay to give up. Always do your best. Study what need to be studied, have self- review and make yourself prepared to take battle again.” (IDI-R2)

Witty supported Smart's claim that success is attainable through continuous effort and belief in oneself. Witty supported that in order to achieve the desired success individual must prepare and equipped herself with knowledge needed to attain one's goals and fulfill personal aspirations. Before taking an exam, an individual must be fully prepared to overcome obstacles and succeed in their endeavors.

“Just keep on trying until you make it. Make yourself equipped to everything in order to succeed or get what you believe you truly deserve.” (IDI-R2)

Positive Outlook

The importance of cultivating a positive mindset to drive constructive actions and achieve favorable results. Smart shared that having a positive mindset enables individual to face challenges resiliently and manifest desired outcomes. Having a positive vision serves as a guiding force, aligning intentions with constructive behaviors. By having optimism and visualizing success, it empowered individual to pursue goals with purpose and determination.

“In order to carry a positive action or have positive outcome, we must develop a positive vision.” (IDI- R2)

Witty resonates that positivity acts as a strong motivator, inspiring her to keep pushing forward towards goals. Staying positive helped her feel more motivated and hopeful, especially when facing difficult situations. It gives her the energy and determination to overcome challenges and believe that anything is achievable.

“It really makes us being more motivated and positive even in tough times, being positive makes enlighten me to make everything possible. and it also serve as a driving force to be more motivated.” (Inf-C2)

Case 3 – Grace

Grace is a 38 years old English teacher who retook the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) for five (5) times and who is currently teaching at Sagayan National High School. She is been teaching for about three (3) years and three (3) months in Department of Education (DepEd). I asked her what name she wants to hide her identity and she said, Grace.

She admitted that being a retaker was challenging; sometimes, she would wonder why others could pass while she could not, hence, causing her to feel embarrassed to socialize or interact with others. However, her determination was one of the reasons she achieved success; she persevered that until the Professional Regulation Commission (PRC) would not close, she will never stop retaking until she passed. And because of her unwavering determination, she finally succeeded and is now employed in the Department of Education (DepEd).

Additionally, when she hadn't yet passed the LET, she became a probationary teacher and taught senior high at Sagayan National High School for about one (1) year even without a license. Her journey exemplifies the significance of resilience and perseverance in overcoming obstacles and attaining one's goals.

Research Question No. 1: What are the experiences of English Teachers in retaking the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET)?

Based on the first research question, there were many themes that have found and these were the themes that had emerged. These were

as follows:

Gaining Self-confidence

Individuals who succeeded in reaching their goals or overcoming challenges, they feel capable and competent, boosting their belief in their abilities. Grace shared that she no longer feels embarrassed, and do not feel like there is no barrier for stopping her when socializing with their fellow teachers. Passing the exam has made her feel much more confident. She felt proud of her accomplishment, and it has helped her overcome any feelings of shame she may have had before. Now, she felt more comfortable interacting with her colleagues.

"I am no longer ashamed, and there is no more barrier in terms of mingling with my co-teachers because even though I am not licensed yet, knowing that I passed, it greatly boosts my confidence." (IDI-R3)

Passing the LET serves as a significant achievement, solidifying individuals' confidence in their readiness to embark on their professional journey as licensed educators. Blessing supported that, success in the LET signifies meeting the professional standards necessary for licensure, validating her competence and capabilities in the field. Achieving this milestone instills a sense of pride and accomplishment, reinforcing her self-esteem and belief in her abilities.

"Passing the LET will really boost our confidence and it will make us proud of our self, because passing the LET means you successfully met the professional standards required for licensed." (Inf- C3)

Unyielding Spirit

A resilient and determined mindset that refuses to give in or surrender, even in the face of adversity or difficulty. Grace asserted that despite feeling ashamed, there is a significant part of her courage urging her to continue. This inner conflict underscores the presence of an unyielding spirit, wherein she acknowledges her vulnerabilities but remains determined to overcome obstacles and pursue goals with resilience and determination.

"...I feel ashamed, but on the other side, there is a big percentage of my courage that really wants me to push through" (IDI-R3)

Blessing supported that, it empowers her to confront challenges and persist despite setbacks, fostering hope and determination. Enables her to face the exam again with resilience, believing in her ability to succeed despite past disappointments. Having an unyielding spirit allows her to maintain strong determination and optimism as she strived to achieve goals.

"Courage plays a significant role to take the LET again. With that, it enabled us to face challenges, believing in our ability to succeed despite past disappointments, it enables us to maintain hope and determination." (Inf-C3)

Choosing Resilience over Adversity

Opting for strength and perseverance in the face of challenges rather than succumbing to them. Grace resonated that in tough times, she might feel unsure at first, but her strong desire to succeed always wins out. Even if she failed before, she never gave up hope or lose trust in herself. She kept pushing forward with determination, believing that she will eventually achieve her goals. Despite setbacks, she remained resilient and confident that she will succeed in the end.

"Even though there may be initial doubts in times of difficulty, my determination to succeed will prevail. Despite failing several times, I never lose hope and faith." (IDI-R3)

Blessing supported that even after experiencing multiple failures, it is important to maintain hope because each setback brings valuable lessons and growth opportunities. By persevering through adversity and remaining determined. Continuous effort and resilience are key to eventually achieving success despite encountering setbacks along the way.

"Despite of failing several times never lose hope because every failure brings us closer to achieving our dreams and keep striving until you succeed." (Inf-C3)

Research Question No. 2: How did the English Teachers re-takers cope with the challenges that they have experienced?

In the second question, Grace was asked about how she cope with the challenges that she experienced after successfully passed the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET). The following themes stated below were thoroughly and were carefully reflected.

Considering Husband as Pillar of Strength

Husband provides emotional stability, encouragement, and reassurance, helping his spouse navigate through feelings of disappointment and frustration. Grace stated that her husband is her primary source of support. Additionally, her husband plays a central role in providing her emotional, practical, and financial support. This support may include encouragement, understanding, and assistance in navigating life's challenges. Grace's husband is portrayed as her most trusted ally and pillar of strength in her journey through life.

"My husband is my number one, he is truly my primary support system." (IDI-R3)

This was supported by Blessing that their support enables individuals to confront challenges with resilience and determination,

motivated by the desire to overcome obstacles not only for themselves but also for the sake of their loved ones. Blessing stated that:

“It serves as a primary support because they provide unconditional love, encouragement, and understanding. Because of our love ones we are able to face challenges because we also strive for them.” (Inf-C3)

Participating Continuous Learning

Continuing learning involves actively engaging in educational activities beyond formal schooling, such as research and attending seminars, to enhance knowledge and skills. Grace stipulated that she is adapting to changes in education by staying updated on new approaches and advancements to better serve the students. By participating in ongoing learning opportunities and seeking input from colleagues, she aimed to stay abreast of developments in education and ensure that her teaching methods remain effective and relevant.

“I am still undergoing research and participating in online seminars because since the approach is different now, you feel that the children are advancing a lot so you need to be more advance in their knowledge, and I also ask for ideas from my co-teachers.” (IDI-R3)

As Blessing supported the assertion of Grace, she stated that seeking advice from co-teachers is beneficial as it provides access to a variety of viewpoints and strategies for tackling challenges. By leveraging the collective wisdom of colleagues, individuals can explore different approaches and solutions, increasing her capacity to address various situations effectively.

“Seeking advice from co-teachers, because we can gain diverse insights and approaches to address challenges and meet expectations.” (Inf-C3)

Striving for Sufficiency

Pursuing success in the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) to improve their financial situation. Grace shared that their current financial circumstances, particularly due to her husband’s job, are insufficient. By striving to pass the LET, she aimed to enhance her career prospects and potentially increase their household income, thereby addressing their financial challenges and achieving sufficiency. She shared that:

“Our financial situation is not really enough, given my husband's job.” (IDI-R3)

Blessing confirmed that aspiration to enhance one's financial situation can serve as a motivating factor for studying diligently and excelling in the LET exam. By obtaining a teaching position through passing the exam, she aimed to secure a stable source of income that can fulfill their needs and contribute to financial stability. The pursuit of a permanent job in teaching is driven by the desire for financial security, which in turn fuels efforts to succeed in the LET.

“The desire to improve financial situation may drive us to study harder and perform better on the LET exam. In order for us to have a permanent job where we can provide our needs or be financially stable.” (Inf-C3)

Looking Forward to Future Prospect

Family's future, particularly future of the children, serves as a powerful motivation for her to persevere and pass the LET exam despite facing numerous setbacks. Grace shared that achieving success in the exam opens doors to stable employment and financial security, ensuring a better future for her family. With each setback, she is reminded of the importance of overcoming obstacles to provide a brighter tomorrow for her loved ones. Hence, she is fueled by a deep sense of responsibility and commitment to ensuring the well-being and prosperity of her family as she continue to pursue success in the LET.

“I am thinking about the future especially the future of my children.” (IDI-R3)

Blessing supported that by passing the LET and can have a stable job, it can access better opportunities to support and provide children's future. This motivation to succeed in the teaching profession reflects a commitment not only to personal advancement but also to creating a better life and brighter prospects for family. Blessing stated that:

“Thinking about becoming licensed teacher, it can secure stable employment and improve their financial situation, which in turn can provide better opportunities for their children. We strive hard not only for our self for also for our family that we can provide them a good life.” (Inf-C3)

Having Strong Faith in God

Grace asserted that by entrusting her aspirations to the Lord and expressed that success in the exam is part of a divine plan for her. This act of prayer reflects a belief in spiritual support and the power of divine intervention to help overcome challenges and achieve goals, providing comfort and reassurance throughout the exam preparation process.

“I just pray to the Lord because I know He will give it to me it is really meant for me.” (IDI-R3)

Blessing as the informant supported Grace saying that she maintained unwavering faith and trust God, despite facing multiple retakes at the LET exam. Her belief in divine guidance and intervention remains steadfast throughout the challenges she encountered. By

anchoring faith in God, she found strength, resilience, and hope to persist in pursuit of success, trusting in His plan for their journey.

“Even though she took the LET multiple times she never lose her faith and trust in God.” (Inf-C3)

Research Question No. 3: What are the insights that can be drawn from the experiences of English Teachers in retaking the Licensure examination that can be shared with their peer and with others in general?

In the third question, it was highlighted the lessons gleaned from the journey of English teacher who undergo the process of retaking the licensure examination can offer valuable wisdom to their colleagues and the wider community. Below were the following themes that emerged during the study.

Resilience and Perseverance

Having resilience and perseverance as important drive force in the face of adversity. Grace shared that not to give up, despite facing repeated failures. By persistently pursuing her goal of passing the LET, she maintained the possibility of eventual success, demonstrating the significance of resilience and determination in overcoming setbacks.

“Do not surrender, even if you fail or fall down several times, just keep pursuing because you can still succeed.” (IDI-R3)

Blessing affirmed that having resilience and perseverance serves as a driving force towards achieving success in the pursuit of licensure. Ultimately, their strong commitment, passion, and belief in themselves set the foundation for their eventual triumph in becoming a licensed teacher.

“The commitment to becoming a licensed teacher speaks volumes about my passion for education and belief in my abilities, determination that undoubtedly led me to success.” (Inf-C3)

Unwavering Determination

Grace expressed that despite encountering hurdles, like retaking the LET exam multiple times, she remained resolute in pursuit of success. Her unyielding commitment is demonstrated by her readiness to confront challenges head-on and tirelessly pursue her objective, exemplifying her unwavering determination. Grace stated that:

“Maybe I am challenged too, I set in my mind before, that until the PRC did not close, I will keep taking it.” (Inf-C3)

Blessing supported that resilience is required to persevere through repeated attempts and emphasizes the significant effort and determination involved in the process. Despite the difficulties, maintaining dedication and positivity is crucial for staying motivated and focused on achieving success.

“Having dedication, always find positivity despite of challenges. Being a retaker for multiple times is not easy.” (Inf-C3)

Always Looking Forward

Regardless of the obstacles encountered, it is crucial to maintain momentum and keep pushing forward. Grace asserted that by staying focused on progress and refusing to succumb to despair, she can navigate adversity with determination and optimism. Hence, his mindset fostered resilience and enables individuals to overcome obstacles, always looking ahead to brighter possibilities despite the difficulties they face. Grace stated that:

“Whatever may happen, just keep moving forward, never lose hope” (Inf-C3)

By maintaining this forward-thinking approach, individuals can navigate obstacles with resilience and optimism, ensuring they remain on the path to achieving their dreams. Blessing supported that in order to succeed it needs to remain dedicated until the goal is attained. She stated that:

“If you want to achieve, don't stop until you achieve that dream” (Inf-C3)

Cross-Case Analysis

The utilization of multiple case studies presented a valuable opportunity to delve into the journey of English teachers who failed the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET) multiple times but eventually succeeded. This approach facilitated the exploration of both commonalities and distinctions among individuals facing similar challenges. It transcended individual cases and instead focused on understanding the broader phenomenon of retake experiences in pursuing their teaching goals. By employing this methodology, a deeper comprehension of the genuine struggles and eventual triumphs of these educators was achieved, with insights emerging directly from their own perspectives.

A case study is a methodological approach that entails a thorough investigation of a certain bounded system while systematically collecting data from various sources. It allows one to look beyond individual case, to the phenomenon; in this case of English teachers' retakers who take the LET multiple times, it helps on dealing with the real experiences of English teachers the secrets that only the informants can generate the real life they possessed. The case study method explored a real-life, contemporary bounded system (a case)

or multiple bounded systems (cases) over time, through detailed, in-depth data collection involving multiple sources of information and reports a case description and case themes (Gustafsson, 2017).

Moreover, according to Brink (2018), a multiple-case design explores a real-life multiple bound system through detailed, in-depth data collection involving sources of information. Through using a multiple-case design a wider exploration of the research question and theoretical evolution will enable the researcher to understand the differences. This enables the researcher to address the complex issues that need to be explored in-depth, and to understand the behavioral conditions of such a system, based on comments inputs and interpretative perspectives of the participants. However, the multiple case study design is a valuable qualitative research tool in studying the links between the personal, social, behavioral, psychological, organizational, cultural, and environmental factors that guide managerial and leadership development.

Case studies are a widely accepted method in social sciences, particularly in fields like education, management, public administration, and social work. This approach provided a framework to analyze the simultaneous occurrences and events within each case, contributing in a more comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon at hand (Baxter, 2008). They provide a comprehensive understanding of individual cases, linking findings to research questions. This approach is particularly useful in practical fields like education, management, and public administration. The design of case studies reflects the reality participant's encounter in their daily lives, offering a lens for understanding contemporary psychological phenomena. Interviews are used to delve deeply into the phenomenon, allowing participants to share their experiences and insights. The approach explores both subjective and objective dimensions of participants' experiences (Mills et al., 2010).

The preceding chapters, particularly Chapters 4 to 6, unveiled the multifaceted experiences of English teachers' retakers who retake the LET exam multiple times but eventually succeeded, as they navigated the challenges in their retake journey and challenges after they successfully passed the LET. The exploration highlighted various themes and central ideas that emerged from each participant's unique case.

Presented were the differences and similarities of experiences of the participants.

Research Question No. 1: What are the experiences of English Teachers in retaking the Licensure Examination for Teachers (LET)?

The researcher interviewed the participants and she ended-up to the four important themes: Experiencing Difficulty in Seeking Job; Building Self-Confidence, Being Determined and Courageous; and Understanding that Teaching in the Field goes beyond Acquiring a License.

Experiencing Difficulty in Seeking Job

Two cases admitted that they have experienced difficulty in seeking job even though they already have a license wherein they experienced rejections in applying. Light encountered challenges in securing employment, as it is required to advance their rank before being eligible to apply for Teacher-I positions. During their job search, Light also experienced setbacks in the form of rejections. She stated:

"Seeking job is not easy, especially applying for teacher-I, I still went through many rejections even though I have a license but I just kept going until I got a job" (IDI-R1)

Smart, the teacher who retook the Licensure examination for Teachers (LET) four (4) times, also agreed to Light that seeking job is the toughest stage, because even though you already have the license does not mean you can easily find a job. She spoke in all sincerity:

"Seeking a job after passing the examination is one of the toughest stage I have experienced, wherein I experienced a lot of rejections" (IDI-R2)

Building Self-Confidence

Passing the LET after retaking it multiple times can uplift self-confidence wherein it represents a commitment to improvement and a willingness to persevere despite setbacks, fostering resilience and determination. It is approbated by Light wherein after multiple failures she finally passed the LET and become a License Professional Teacher. For her, failures are part of success. She said:

Having a strong determination contributed a lot to me. Failing an examination once is not a hindrance in achieving ones goal. Being determined and having enough courage to take again the examination, be able to give my best, and be able to pass the examination" (IDI-R2).

Furthermore, Smart supported this by stating that upon passing the LET, she indeed experienced a surge in self-confidence, which provided her with hope that she could finally pursue teaching in the classroom. She shared:

"Personally, passing the examination uplift my confidence as it is a passport in being able to teach in the classroom or in institution." (IDI-R2)

Table 2. *The Experiences of English Teachers Retakers*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Experiencing Difficulty in Seeking Job	<p>“Seeking job is not easy, especially applying for teacher-I, I still went through many rejections even though I have a license but I just kept going until I got a job” – IDI-R1</p> <p>“Seeking a job after passing the examination is one of the toughest stages I have experienced, wherein I experienced a lot of rejections” IDI-R2</p>
Building Self- Confidence	<p>“Passing the LET has made a big impact on me as a teacher and especially I gain more self-confidence, to be strong-willed, courageous, not to give up easily on life’s challenges because even though there are many failures and I have to wait a long time for the license but it is not an obstacle if we have goals that we want to achieve” –IDI-R1</p> <p>“Personally, passing the examination uplift my confidence as it is a passport in being able to teach in the classroom or in institution” – IDI-R2</p> <p>“I am no longer ashamed, and there’s no more barrier in terms of mingling with my co-teachers because even though I am not licensed yet, knowing that I passed, it greatly boosts my confidence” – IDI-R3</p>
Being Determined and Courageous	<p>“Having a strong determination contributed a lot to me. Failing an examination once is not a hindrance in achieving one’s goal. Being determined and having enough courage to take again the examination, be able to give my best, and be able to pass the examination.” –IDI-R2</p> <p>“Even though there may be initial doubts in times of difficulty, my determination to succeed will prevail. Despite failing several times, I never lose hope and faith.” –IDI-R3</p> <p>“...I feel ashamed, but on the other side, there’s a big percentage of my courage that really wants me to push through...” –IDI-R3</p>
Understanding that Teaching in the Field Goes Beyond Acquiring a License	<p>“Even though I passed the exam and have the license already, there are processes to go through before I can work in the department, but it’s okay, I didn’t complain because I believe that there is right timing as long as you do all the efforts to achieve what you want.” –IDI-R1</p> <p>“Passing the Licensure examination doesn’t mean you have reached your goal, because me personally, waited for my chance to finally teach in the classroom and it is another stage in my life which I find difficult.” –IDI-R2</p>

Additionally, Grace admitted that since passing the LET, she has felt more comfortable interacting with others, including her colleagues, without experiencing shyness. She then enclosed:

“I am no longer ashamed, and there is no more barrier in terms of mingling with my co-teachers because even though I am not licensed yet, knowing that I passed, it greatly boosts my confidence.” (IDI-R3)

Being Determined and Courageous

Being determined and courageous in facing failures allows individuals to persevere through difficulties, maintaining focus and motivation despite obstacles. Light expressed that her determination and courage were instrumental in her decision to retake the exam multiple times until she achieved success. She said:

“Having a strong determination contributed a lot to me. Failing an examination once is not a hindrance in achieving one’s goal. Being determined and having enough courage to take again the examination, be able to give my best, and be able to pass the examination.” (IDI-R2)

Moreover, Grace admitted that despite encountering failures and failing the LET on multiple times, her determination ultimately guided her to achieve the success she enjoys today. She said:

“Even though there may be initial doubts in times of difficulty, my determination to succeed will prevail. Despite failing several times, I never lose hope and faith” (IDI-R3)

Furthermore, possessing courage greatly assist her in persevering despite the humiliations she endured as a result of retaking the LET multiple times. She also shared:

“...I feel ashamed, but on the other side, there is a big percentage of my courage that really wants me to push through...” (IDI-R3)

Understanding that Teaching in the Field Goes Beyond Acquiring a License

Having a license does not automatically mean you are ready to teach, you have to go through a process might involve finding a job, gaining experience, or completing additional training before you can start teaching. Light affirmed that before working in the department, she underwent several procedures. She said:

“Even though I passed the exam and have the license already, there are processes to go through before I can work in the department wherein complying all the papers, rank up and wait, but it’s okay, I did not complain because I believe that there is right timing as long as you do all the efforts to achieve what you want.” (IDI-R1)

Additionally, Smart also supported Light’s claim that she also waited for her time to finally teach in the classroom and went through

also with the processes. She uttered:

“Passing the Licensure examination does not mean you have reached your goal, because me personally, waited for my chance to finally teach in the classroom and it is another stage in my life which I find difficult.” (IDI-R2)

Research Question No. 2: How did the English Teachers re-takers cope with the challenges that they have experienced?

In the data the researcher has gathered, she concluded four (4) emerging themes. These include the following: Having Family as a Pillar of Support; Imbibing Faith as a Source of Strength; Thinking of Family’s Future, Sacrifices and Educational Goals; and Being Hopeful of the Right Time.

Having Family as a Pillar of Support

The support and encouragement from family members can provide the motivation and determination needed to keep trying, even after multiple failures. Knowing that they have a supportive network behind them can give the individual the strength to persevere and eventually succeed in passing the LET. Three cases mentioned that their families served as a support network and a source of motivation to persist and retake the LET until they succeeded. Light expressed that her family serves as her driving force to continue pursuing her goals despite facing obstacles.

Table 3. *The Coping Mechanism of English Teachers Re-takers*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Having Family as a Pillar of Support	<p>“My family, they never stopped giving me love, encouragement and support to keep going until I passed. That is why I did everything for them. They are my inspiration along with the help of grace of our Lord.” –IDI-R1</p> <p>“My family is one of my inspirations and source of motivation to try again until I passed and became a teacher.” –IDI-R2</p> <p>“My husband is my number one, he is truly my primary support system.” –IDI-R3</p>
Imbibing Faith as a Source of Strength	<p>“Honestly, I feel pressure and nervous but I’m always praying to God to help me, guide me, and give me knowledge and wisdom to become an effective teacher to my students.” –IDI-R1</p> <p>“Reminding myself that it’s okay if I didn’t do or meet their expectations and standards, as long as I did my best, remain focus and always praying to God and ask for guidance.” –IDI-R2</p> <p>“I just pray to the Lord because I know He will give it to me it is really meant for me.” –IDI-R3</p>
Thinking of Family’s Future, Sacrifices, and Educational Goals	<p>“The dream of my family, the difficulty and hard work of my parents to earn money and buy food, the expenses of my parents to send my siblings to school, my desire to secure my family’s future and my dream to teach are the reason why I keep going in achieving/pursuing teaching despite of challenges I have experienced.” – IDI-R1</p> <p>“I am thinking about the future especially the future of my children.” –IDI-R3</p> <p>“Our financial situation isn’t really enough, given my husband’s job.” –IDI-R3</p>
Being Hopeful of the Right Time	<p>“I will just think about my family and the Lord’s will, I know for myself that when the right time comes, I will be given an item and I can work in DEPED” –IDI-R1</p> <p>“Practicing gratitude, being thankful to everything, believe in myself because every prayer comes with an answer and everything has its perfect timing” IDI-R2</p>

She said:

“My family, they never stopped giving me love, encouragement and support to keep going until I passed. That is why I did everything for them. They are my inspiration along with the help of grace of our Lord” (IDI-R1)

Smart went on to elucidate, explaining that her family give her emotional comfort, reassurance, and encouragement when facing the negative emotions and setbacks. She uttered:

“My family is one of my inspirations and source of motivation to try again until I passed and became a teacher” (IDI-R2)

Furthermore, the steadfast support and motivation from a spouse can equip the downs. She said:

“My husband is my number one, he is truly my primary support system” (IDI-R3)

Imbibing Faith as a Source of Strength

Faith can be a powerful resource for coping with setbacks and challenges in life by providing spiritual comfort, perseverance, moral guidance, community support, and coping mechanisms to navigate difficulties. Light shared to the researcher that whenever she felt pressured, she keeps on praying and asking guidance to the Lord.

She said:

“Honestly, I feel pressure and nervous but I am always praying to God to help me, guide me, and give me knowledge and wisdom to become an effective teacher to my students.” (IDI-R1)

Moreover, having a strong faith in God acts as a potent support system.

She said:

“Reminding myself that it is okay if I did not do or meet their expectations and standards, as long as I did my best, remain focus and always praying to God and ask for guidance” (IDI-R2)

Furthermore, Grace supported this by confirming that conviction through prayer and faith, one can align themselves with what is truly destined for them, finding comfort and assurance in the belief that God will provide what is meant for them. She shared:

“I just pray to the Lord because I know He will give it to me it is really meant for me.” (IDI-R3)

Thinking of Family’s Future, Sacrifices, and Educational Goals

By keeping in mind, the family's sacrifices, future, and educational goals, an individual can find the necessary motivation, resilience, emotional support, and sense of purpose to persist and succeed in passing the LET, despite the many challenges they may face. Light affirmed that by her family's dreams, her parents' sacrifices, her goal to secure their future, and her love for teaching motivate her to pursue an education career despite challenges.

Moreover, thinking about family’s future and providing a good life for children can give you a strong reason to keep going, even when facing difficulties. Grace highlighted that the drive to create a better future for family can motivate you to persevere through challenges.

She said:

“I am thinking about the future especially the future of my children” (IDI-R3)

She also added that the goal of improving the family's financial stability can drive her to persist. Even though the financial situation may be challenging, the desire to secure a better future for the family and the goal to be financially stable can provide a powerful sense of purpose and motivation to overcome the obstacles of repeatedly taking the LET. She noted:

“Our financial situation is not really enough, given my husband's job” (IDI-R3)

Being Hopeful of the Right Time

Despite facing challenges and setbacks along the way maintaining a positive outlook and trust that success will come at the appropriate moment. Light stated that she is hopeful and patient attitude. Trusting in a higher power and the belief that the right opportunity will present itself at the appropriate time, rather than forcing or rushing the situation. She said that:

“I will just think about my family and the Lord’s will, I know for myself that when the right time comes, I will be given an item and I can work in DepEd.” (IDI-R1)

In addition to this, Smart stated that a mindset of gratitude, faith, and patience, where the individual trusts in God's plan and timing, even when the path forward is unclear, believing that their prayers will be answered. She said that:

“Practicing gratitude, being thankful to everything, believe in myself because every prayer comes with an answer and everything has its perfect timing” (IDI-R2)

Research Question No. 3: What are the insights that can be drawn from the experiences of English Teachers in retaking the Licensure examination that can be shared with their peer and with others in general?

In the data the researcher has gathered, she concluded three (3) emerging themes. These include the following: Resilience and Perseverance; Preparation Leads to Success; and Commitment to One’s Chosen Profession.

Resilience and Perseverance

Being resilient and persevering helped them recover from setbacks, stay positive, and continue moving forward despite failures. Resilience helps individuals adjust to changes and bounce back from challenges, while perseverance allows them to keep going in tough times and reach their goals. It was shared by Light that:

“Just keep going, do not give up, make an effort and ask the Lord for help because He will always give it in His right timing.” (IDI-R1)

Smart also shared that maintaining a positive mindset and a mindset-focused on growth helps her become stronger and keep going when things get tough, and eventually succeed even if they face setbacks at the beginning. She shared that:

“In order to carry a positive action or have positive outcome, we must develop a positive vision.” –IDI-R2

Grace also added that she is determined to keep trying to take the LET even when it is hard, keeping in mind to keep retaking the LET until she passed or until the PRC does not close. She stated that:

“I am challenged too, I set in my mind before, that until the PRC does not close, I will keep taking it.” –IDI-R3

Preparation Leads to Success

Being prepared, checking your own progress, and not giving up helps them gain knowledge, confidence, and strength to overcome difficulties you they faced before. This leads to passing the exam and achieving their dream of becoming a teacher. Light affirmed that studying extensively before an exam ensures you're prepared to tackle it confidently, leading to success. Being well-prepared equips you to face challenges effectively, whether it's in an exam, battle, or teaching scenario, ultimately resulting in a positive outcome. She shared that:

“Before you enter a big war, you must be prepared. Before you take the exam, make sure that you studied well. Just like teaching students before you discuss your lesson, make sure you are well prepared, and know the lesson very well so that if the student has a question, you can explain it to them well” –IDI-R1

Smart shared that while failing may happen, it is crucial not to let it discourage you from trying again. Instead, one should learn from their mistakes, do their best, and prepare thoroughly for future challenges. By adopting this mindset and continually striving to improve, success becomes attainable despite setbacks along the way. She said that:

“It is better to fail than not trying at all, it is okay to fail but it's not okay to give up. Always do your best. Study what need to be studied, have self-review and make yourself prepared to take battle again.” (IDI-R2)

Table 4. *The Insights of English Teachers in Retaking the Licensure Examination*

<i>Emerging Themes</i>	<i>Supporting Statements</i>
Resilience and Perseverance	“Just keep going, don't give up, make an effort and ask the Lord for help because He will always give it in His right timing” –IDI-R1 “In order to carry a positive action or have positive outcome, we must develop a positive vision” –IDI-R2 “I'm challenged too, I set in my mind before, that until the PRC doesn't close I'll keep taking it” –IDI-R3
Preparation Leads to Success	“Before you enter a big war, you must be prepared. Before you take the exam, make sure that you studied well. Just like teaching students before you discuss your lesson, make sure you are well prepared, and know the lesson very well so that if the student has a question, you can explain it to them well” –IDI-R1 “It really requires you to be prepared at all times and have a positive mindset and faith in God” –Inf-C1 “It's better to fail than not trying at all, it is okay to fail but it's not okay to give up. Always do your best. Study what need to be studied, have self-review and make yourself prepared to take battle again” –IDI-R2 “Just keep on trying until you make it or get what you believe you truly deserve” –Inf-C2
Commitment to One's Chosen Profession	“The goal I have set for myself is that I will not waste the favor given by the Lord. I will use it for the goodness that can give a great help to the children and be an inspiration to others” –IDI-R1 “To inspire others and serving the children as she serves the Lord is her goal she set for herself” –Inf-C1 “It makes me more dedicated to my profession. I will never waste or take for granted this opportunity or chance given to me. I will forever be passionate to this commitment” –IDI-R2 “Being a retaker, passing the LET and be a licensed teacher would greatly impact to our confidence and be dedicated to profession” –Inf-C2

Commitment to One's Chosen Profession

Passing the exam is seen as a very important moment because it makes them feel more confident and committed to teaching. This shows how much they care about being teachers, wanting to help others, and being dedicated and passionate about their work. Light supported that she will never take for granted the chance has given to her to become a Licensed Professional Teacher (LPT). She stated that:

“The goal I have set for myself is that I will not waste the favor given by the Lord. I will use it for the goodness that can give a great help to the children and be an inspiration to others.” (IDI-R1)

Finally, Smart affirmed that passing the LET exam makes her even more dedicated to being a teacher. It makes her more determined to fully commit and put her whole effort into being a teacher, which is their chosen career. She said that:

“It makes me more dedicated to my profession. I will never waste or take for granted this opportunity or chance given to me. I will forever be passionate to this commitment” (IDI-R2)

Conclusions

In conclusion, the participants have discussed their experiences, struggles, coping strategies, and insights. Even if you have passed the LET and have a license, it does not mean it is easy to apply for a job. There are still processes that need to be complied with, especially with the Department of Education (DEPED). The results also highlighted the importance of having determination because without the determination to continue despite the failures you have faced, you cannot become successful.

Furthermore, as I conducted interviews and listened to the responses of the participants, I found myself deeply moved. Their stories

ignited a fire within me, serving as a source of inspiration and motivation to persevere in the face of challenges and pursue the success I aspire to achieve. Their resilience and determination resonated with me, reinforcing the belief that with dedication and hard work, overcoming obstacles is possible. Their words encouraged me to maintain a positive mindset and to continue striving towards my goals, even when faced with adversity.

Moreover, my experience with the academic journey in its entirety has proven to be immensely fulfilling. Furthermore, I have derived significant advantages from this comprehensive project, serving as an opportunity to propel my career forward. Through this endeavor, my research interests have been broadened even further, allowing me to explore new horizons and deepen my understanding of various subjects. This experience has not only enriched my academic pursuits but has also equipped me with valuable skills and insights that will contribute to my professional growth and development in the long run.

Moreover, there were two theories supporting the result of the study. First Self- Efficacy Theory which delve to an individual's belief in their ability to succeed in specific situations or accomplish particular tasks. This theory was highlighted by the English teachers' retakers as attested to two of the themes in the study which is the, 'Being Determined and Courageous' and "Resilience and Perseverance." With high self- efficacy are more likely to exhibit determination and courage in the face of failure. They possess a strong belief in their capabilities to overcome obstacles and achieve success, which fuels their motivation to persevere despite setbacks.

Lastly, the Structural-Functional theory which has been highlighted by the English teachers' retakers as attested to one of the themes "Family as Pillar of Support" It was recommended the role of families in offering encouragement, reassurance, and comfort to retakers during times of stress and uncertainty. Family members serve as a source of emotional validation and solidarity, fostering a sense of belonging and security for retakers as they strive to achieve their professional goals.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Kristine Mae M. Sodoy

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology – Philippines

Kristy Jane R. Muegna, PhD

Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology – Philippines